

Representational Model Guided by AI Algorithmic Logic Procedures

Silvia Laurentiz¹

ORCID: [0000-0003-4212-0441](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4212-0441)

University of São Paulo, Brazil

laurentz@usp.br

ABSTRACT

This article presents the current outcomes of the research project Conformed Thought and Art in the Context of Algorithmic Logic and AI Procedures (FAPESP No. 2023/05500-3). The investigation was prompted by the generation of an unexpected image by an artificial intelligence system—a phenomenon often referred to as a “machine hallucination.” This event serves as a starting point for analyzing the logical structures embedded in the conceptual and perceptual models that inform creative processes in computational contexts. The study also examines how artistic practices contribute to critical reflections on what we define as Conformed Thought, a concept developed in earlier publications [7, 8, 10, 11, 12]. The project proposes a representational model oriented by information processing that interrogates the epistemological and operational dimensions of computational algorithms, with particular attention to artificial intelligence. A central concern raised is that the indiscriminate use of AI-generated content in training datasets may lead to irreversible degradation of cultural production. The current stage of the research involves the development of an artwork based on the technical and aesthetic studies conducted so far.

Keywords

Artificial Intelligence, Signs, Logic, Art

1 Introduction

Faced with the generation, by an AI process², of an unexpected image, which could be identified as a “machine hallucination”³, this work aims to analyze logical procedures in conceptual and perceptual models involved in creative processes, reflecting on art's contributions to what we call “conformed thoughts”. The term “conformed thought” has been defined in several publications [7, 9, 10, 11, 12] as: codes and set of codes, norms, algorithms, standards, devices, interfaces, since they are the results of scientific concepts, texts, and theories and, therefore, updated forms of elaborated knowledge, with the ability to change habits and behaviors. This research is still in progress and can be described from the following arguments: in our daily lives, we extensively exercise and practice logical-abstract-symbolic reasoning, which we call ‘conformed thoughts’, self-controlled and deliberate, the result of concepts, models of knowledge of a culture or group, and this means that we are adapting and changing habits, behaviors, beliefs and actions based on these patterns. Consequently, this will cause changes in our way of thinking. The main interest is to present a representational model promoted by information processing that can point out questions about computational algorithms, artificial intelligence in particular. In summary, we have been studying machine training models in generative AI and initially; to understand the process, we proposed a simple task of generating images of apples.

¹ Professor at the Department of Fine Arts and the Graduate Program in Visual Arts at the School of Communications and Arts at the School of Communications and Arts, University of São Paulo. PhD in Communication and Semiotics (PUC-SP) and Habilitation (Livres-Docência) in Arts (ECA / USP). Founder and leader of the Realities Research and Extension Group (www.eca.usp.br/realidades).

² In this article, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a branch of computing that includes machine learning techniques that use a database, usually in huge quantities, to extract information and knowledge. We are interested here in techniques that make machines autonomous agents, that is, capable of acting without human interference.

³ Sometimes AI algorithms produce outputs that don't make sense or are entirely inaccurate, either because they've been incorrectly decoded or don't follow an identifiable pattern. In this case, it is often said metaphorically that the machine has hallucinated. Machine misinterpretations occur due to several factors, including overfitting, bias/inadequacy in training data, and high model complexity.

The idea, from the beginning, was not to use prompts or any labels that could indicate that the images used from a public image bank were of apples. The proposal was to work with a stable diffusion model, where noise is progressively added to an image until all that remains is random noise. Knowing how to identify the added noise, by its subsequent subtraction, the system can identify patterns in the images; and after the training phase, it will be able to generate images from the learned pattern. Interestingly, sometimes unexpected resulting images happened that could not be immediately accurately identified as an apple image, despite the database being only composed of images of apples. And in this process, we realized there was damage caused by the indiscriminate use of content generated by machine learning, leading to some irreversible damage in the resulting models, where the traces of the original content even disappear. Authors Iliia Shumailov et al. refer to this effect as “model collapse” [15]. Therefore, the research, at this moment, is concerned with these deviations caused by training from large-scale data, which will significantly affect our representational model.

Looking at [Figure 1](#), we can immediately see that it is an abstract image, with some voluminous shapes, colors from an intense red to green, earthy tones, white. There is an exuberance of red, which carries a sensory charge in the image.

There is also an oscillation with the green tone, its complementary. And at first, we identified a background where the most voluminous shape centered on the image seems to be supported. We have no other information that can confirm whether this image was AI-generated, nor have we identified a label that may have been used.

However, one thing that was not expected from AI, when we started this research, was its ability to interpret abstract information like the one in this image. We uploaded this image to ChatGPT (OpenAI, 2024) and asked it to describe it. The answer was surprising from the beginning, when that image was defined as “abstract art”. Not an abstract image, but art. After a formal description of the image, it added: “This type of abstract art can be interpreted in many ways, depending on the perspective of the viewer. The shapes and colors can evoke different emotions or personal memories. Overall, the image conveys a sense of intensity and dynamism”.

We continue to question ChatGPT about representational aspects, for example, how to identify objects and forms in the image. At the end we asked if any

fruit can be recognized in the image, and we received a new surprise with the answer: “(...) could be seen as something similar to an apple (...)”.

1 Initial Premises

Figure 1: Image generated by AI in a preliminary procedure to the representational model proposed in the research. Source: by Author.

Given this preliminary condition, the project we developed begins with the recognition of units of meaning in a representational model, based on things, objects, and models [10]. In this proposed model, in a process of representation we have 'things in themselves', 'objects', which will be objectified things (things in themselves only enter a communicative system while objectified), and 'models' of these objects.

Thus, in the proposed system, there will be minimum units of representation. However, it is not a simple linear system, nor is it a closed deterministic system. We have influences and new inputs, interferences and information inserted by the context, disturbances and changes caused by the path. But, one thing is objectified to participate in a communication system, which is transformed based on goals and objectives (and at this initial moment, the goals and objectives are given by external agents). Then the result is a concept of this object transformed into a model that will return to the system again by feedback ([Figure 2](#)).

Figure 2: Basic system of representation based on the minimum units: things, objects and models, recognized as thoughts conformed to the diagram. Source: by Author.

Figure 3: Interpretation of Vilém Flusser's Abstraction Climb, based on AI-generated images. Source: by Author.

2 Development

We follow by feedback, from the cybernetic model, where the process will move to the next phase, when the objectified thing will be transformed by an external purpose, generating results again, thus infinitely. Therefore, when we say that the purpose is ordered by agents externally to the system, it is different from when the system itself has autonomy to change its goals. But in any case, it is a complex system, which means that it may be capable of generating emergent patterns, and by entropy generate unpredictable behaviors, disorganization, or suffer technical or human

interference, introduce randomness, information overload, among others.

According to Flusser, imagination is essential for our actions and understanding of the world [4]. However, at the same time, imagination is our ability to distance ourselves from the objects of the world. This movement of moving away and retreating objects can be called abstraction. There is an example in his book *The Coded World* [4] that deals with the inaugural gesture of creating images, when in prehistoric caves we find the figuration of a horse. Flusser says:

“the first image setters had to move away from a horse, look at it and then fix this fleeting vision on the cave wall, precisely so that others could recognize it” [4, p. 162].

The fundamental question, Flusser continues, is: where do you go when you move away from the horse?

Then we have the image of a thing, then the explanation of that image of the thing, and then an image of that explanation, which will result in concepts and finally in the model of the object of the thing itself. I believe that Flusser's theory has already been widely disseminated, unnecessary to prolong this point. Our problem is that with algorithmic procedures, confirming the Flusserian theory, imagetive thinking is becoming capable of re-elaborating concepts, capable of transforming concepts into objects, and becoming a meta-thought of a conceptual way of thinking [4, p. 118]. He also says that imagetive thinking starts to think about concepts, in the form of models [4, p. 118]. More categorically, he continues the next page that imagetive thought takes the place of philosophy, as a *metaprocessing* of concepts.

With AI – where we perceive a new dimension of Flusser's abstraction scale (Figure 3), the machine not only classifies and analyzes information, but also creates phenomena from the synthesis of numerous models. Therefore, the process continues, to the point that AI itself establishes new goals, objectives and habits, and in this case, by agents internal to the system, that is, it manages to establish new goals internally.

The consequences that this may cause in cultural production. And yet, AI is no longer just a tool or language and becomes an agent capable of carrying out technological mediations, influencing cultural production, promoting social interactions, generating new cultural paradigms.

This should be considered, before proceeding: the various possible approaches to AI: - as a Tool; - as a Language; - as Mediation; - as Culture.

In addition, a) as a tool, it can be used as an AI-assisted creative process, Human-AI co-creation, and fully automated creation; b) As a language, we can recognize a traditional style with AI, whether abstract or experimental, more photorealistic, and even as generative and interactive art; c) As technological mediation, we can approach AI through Natural Language Processing (NLP), as Adversarial Generative Models (GANs), as personalization and recommendation

⁴ We cannot fail to recognize that AI is currently a producer of content on platforms, repositories, cultural curatorship, and acts in different forms of social interaction. Social networks with bots and virtual assistants interact with users on social media platforms influencing online discussions and behaviors. Not to mention ethical issues and the

algorithms, as interaction and communication; and d) As culture, where AI acts as an influencer in cultural production, as a repository and cultural curatorship, as a cultural reflection (through biases, narratives, and dissemination of information), as a form of social interaction (social networks, bots, virtual assistants), as cultural ethics (privacy, surveillance, autonomy and control, Fake News), and as a creator of new cultural paradigms.

Which means, for example, that we are currently surrounded by platforms and social interactions impregnated by AI algorithms and that, we cannot stay only in the discursiveness of the technique, AI is now considered as a culture⁴ and not just a tool. We must consider technology itself in cultural relational practices, by the social fabric in behavioral terms. Today, social networks already work with AIs, which shape us, and form our culture, and this is the basis of the principle of Conformed Thought that we follow in our project. This principle recognizes all these approaches to AIs.

Returning, after this quick clarification, from the abstractive escalation of representation in the diagrams to a representational model, we move on to the next step, which is to create a dynamic cybernetic machine based on a learning model, which will synthesize data to generate representational objects in a *metaprocessing* of/for the generation of "conformed thoughts". It is already clear at this point that there is a subtle difference between 1. if it has the image of something that is absent - and much has already been said about this (and I recall the principle of phantasmagoria); of 2. if it has a modelling process that metaprocesses and generates its own objectified models. In other words, we are not just saying that we have a simulation of the imagination [4, p. 169], in the face of the much-discussed question of whether or not simulation is representation [2, pp. 37-48]; nor citing the proposal of the digital to lead to a dimensionless condition [4, p. 176] with possibilities of information of infinite recombination and signal superpositions..., but, in addition, what we are adding in this process is the quasi- autonomy of the machine and decision-making.

From Figure 4 we can see the machine learning model, which we call metacognitive quasi-process⁵,

culture of the algorithm, biases, dissemination of information and Fake News.

⁵ The concept of "metacognitive quasi-process" is presented in [14, p. 10]. Just to make it easier to read at this point, we can say that considering the representational system proposed in Figure 2, in Figure 4 the representational system starts to reevaluate its objectives and goals

presented in the project Conformed Thought and Art in the context of algorithmic logic and AI procedures [14, p. 10]. Thus, in the escalation of Flusser's abstraction, we go through important setbacks and distances to what we arrive at in the synthesis of a machine trained by concepts that will feed back into the system in *metaprocessing*, or metacognition. But it is worth a new regression, before the current phase, to approach AI processes, images of apples were generated from prompts in the main current AI generators, always with the same request: Generate an image of an apple. We can remember Baudrillard at this moment and his concept of Hyperreal, where the technical image becomes more real than the real, that is, an idealized representation of the real that starts to cause us real effects [1]. A reality produced by models, signs and images that no longer have direct reference to the real world, but that seem more real than real.

And what happens when hyperreality blurs the boundary between the real and the fictional? When the

hyperreal becomes an epiphenomenon, that is, it becomes part of a mental imagery that causes an effect beyond that under its primary consideration. In other words, when do parallel and secondary phenomena take the lead to the main phenomenon and reestablish the parameters of reality?

In this way, we can already deduce that AIs incessantly produce and reproduce images and representations that replace direct contact with reality, reestablishing new parameters for reality. And, while hyperreal, considered an epiphenomenon as well as a superficial manifestation - let's call it that, of reality - AIs start to overcome barriers and give credibility to their images in an inversion of the representational process: the real phenomenon becomes secondary and superficial, since the machine places us at a distance from the objects of the world that confuse us between real and fictional.

Figure 4: extended diagram for representational model using AIs. Source: by Author.

through the Machine Learning process. This means that the system makes its decisions internally, with a certain autonomy, without an order from an external system. In this case, the representational model processes itself, metaprocessing its data. In this paper, we consider

metaprocessing of a representational system as a metacognitive process. Since it does not fulfill all the characteristics of cognition, we will call it "metacognitive quasi-process".

Figure 5: image generated in Stable Diffusion Online (<https://stablediffusion.com/>) - a free Artificial Intelligence image generator that efficiently creates high-quality images from text prompts. Do not confuse the technique of Generative Artificial Intelligence stable diffusion models. There are libraries and tools that can be employed to make it immensely easier to implement or use these templates, as is the case with this website. Source: by the Author.

Figure 6: Images generated by the initial attempts of our machine learning model, stable diffusion. Source: by the Author.

Thus, the first phase of generating images by different generators currently available has always started from models already trained, exactly to perceive this dynamic, the blurring of borders. The models of DALL-E, Flux.ai, Krea.ia, ChatGPT, Stable Diffusion, were used at this time, and we can already perceive subtle differences between the different models trained, some more realistic, others more illustrative, or with some deviations, which further highlights the proportions and effects in current cultural production.

Figure 7: Images generated by our already improved machine learning model. Source: by the Author.

In addition to this preliminary process, using prompts in different trained models, in our research we have been training our own model, from a public database of apples. Again, in this case, we have not been using prompts or labels. It is a semi-supervised training system, where we have been working with a stable diffusion model (and we did not use the online stable diffusion, as used to generate [Figure 5](#)). We use a U-Net model, which are convolutional neural networks. Quickly, the amount of noise in the latent space is estimated and subtracted from the training image. This process is repeated several times, reducing the noise according to the steps specified by the programmer.

In this process of noise insertion and subtraction, the network gradually recovered patterns in the image, while changing parameters until different training results were achieved. We did not identify, for example, the same characteristics of the current market models, used in the

preliminary phase, because our model is a simplified version of machine learning. The idea was never to compete with large technology conglomerates, nor to achieve the same results, but to demonstrate the fragility and risks of these systems. Especially because this is theoretical research, which is based on practical experiments, and not the reverse.

Remembering that, after the training process, we moved on to a process of discrimination of those generated images that better represent the model from another trained network, now with the reference of apples defined by labels. This second network identifies among those images generated by our model, based on the following criteria: those with a higher level of confidence (we are establishing 90%), those with low confidence (below 90), and those not recognized. Of course, images with 90 to 100% confidence choose more realistic apples while the others are distancing themselves from an immediate apple recognition. But we remember that the discriminator used was trained with this profile, so the result will always tend to identify "more realistic" apples. Therefore, we can immediately say that the image presented in [Figure 1](#) would be discarded. However, motivated exactly by that image, we also started to count those images with low confidence, as well as those totally discarded, because we are also interested in perceiving a latent space of the generated images. And, at first, images that end up falling short of expectations and present unexpected results are considered by some authors as 'machine hallucinations', and it is evident that to question a model of a representational system this can be interesting in the future.

Just to better exemplify the process, in [Figure 6](#) there were the first attempts to generate images, still with adjustments and initial studies. In [Figure 7](#) the model now generates more realistic apples images, but some inconsistencies and inaccuracies can be noticed.

3 Some Considerations

Some initial considerations after the initial testing phase with the prototype: - The algorithm efficiently generates and selects apples; - At each iteration it is possible to verify a change in the pattern of apple generation, motivated by the apples generated in the processes; - According to the initial plan, we were forcing the system to be fed back, returning to the initial base of the image bank those that were considered highly reliable in the first generation, after the model had already been trained. With the initial database expanded,

new training is done. After this training, new images are generated, new discrimination, recursively, for at least 3 generations of images. This is consistent with Ilia Shumailov et al., when they demonstrate the same concern, right at the beginning of the article, that if the training data of most future models are also extracted from the web, they will inevitably train based on the data produced by their predecessors [[15, p. 755](#)]. In the final phase, it is intended to analyze the entire process again.

The focus was to provide feedback on the training continuously. If in fact, according to a 2022 EUROPOL Innovation Lab report, which predicted that 90% of online content would be generated by AI by 2026 [[3](#)], this, consequently, means that AI-generated images will feed back into all other systems and internet agents as well, and that they will fill our feeds. These images, crowding our access and search systems, will end up impacting on our representation models, proliferating images that are increasingly distant from their initial objects, causing an overload of information available with reduced quality. So much so that research conducted by Europol shows that the most worrying trends are in the evolution and detection of deepfakes and disinformation in general. Of course, everyone knows what a deepfake is and what legal, ethical, and moral damages are involved in this matter. In this project, in line with Flusser [[4](#)], we are interested in the passage from a thing that was objectified to a model, and this model later becoming an objectified model, which subsequently becomes a model of the model and that these processes carry levels of abstractions that are increasingly distant from the "thing in itself". This is the proposal of Flusser's abstraction scale and in our proposed model from a basic unit of representation we suggest that the process of modeling and learning would cause a *metaprocessing* of/for the generation of 'conformed thoughts'. In other words, when a discussion is initiated about false information (deepfakes, falsity of documents, misuse of images, invasion of privacy, alteration of data in political campaigns, generation of false criminal evidence...) created and distributed on the network, ethical issues are easily detected by purposely participating in this process. However, our project raises the issue that even without being images generated by some dubious principle and in bad faith, something happens in the generation of images that will cause irreversible consequences in the representational system.

It is important to warn that in 2024 the 2022 EUROPOL report was contested and had an updated

version that replaced the previous version exactly at the point where they declare the expected future share of 90% of content synthetically generated by AI [3]. This information in the updated version was removed in 2024. Despite this, we still believe it is a worrying prediction. Even though it's not 90% of AI content, it's currently shown to be a significant number. In conclusion, in scenarios where new models are trained by data generated by other models, this can cause accumulated degeneracy. Over time we will have a loss of variety, fidelity and the ability to generalize. Especially because we are dealing with errors, biases and simplifications that accumulate, and with that, as Flusser predicted, the model moves further away from the things of the world. And, if before we sought to distinguish true information from false, when we start to deal with models, this seems to no longer make sense.

In addition, it is evident that closed systems that feedback infinitely tend to generate disorder and randomness by entropy, and this is also a cause for concern. In the next steps, in our model we intend to bring the contribution of the arts, allowing the system to adapt and compensate for the loss of information, in addition to containing a subjective bias of the object of the model. In this way, the architecture of the proposed system that comprises the generator, the discriminator, the clusterizer and the selector of images, we propose to intervene, guided by the motivation of the project Conformed Thought and Art in the context of algorithmic logic and AI procedures, bringing a bias of art to the next stages of the work.

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